

PANEL SESSION :

Title: "Future-Proofing Power Control Centers: A Cross-Sectoral View"

Panelists: Experts from TSO, DSO, RCC, Aggregator, and RES Operators

SUBMISSION TIMELINE:

Abstract submission deadline: April 10, 2026

Notification of abstract acceptance: April 15, 2026

Full paper submission deadline: April 30, 2026

Notification of full paper acceptance: May 20, 2026

Final paper submission: June 5, 2026

Conference dates: June 22-23, 2026

CONTACT INFORMATION:

All official updates and the latest information can be found on our website:

 www.demsee.org

For correspondence regarding abstracts, full paper submissions, and questions related to the panel session, please write to:

 info@demsee.org

Registration: On-site, 22nd June 2026, 08:30-09:00
(free of charge)

18TH DEMSEE ANNUAL CONGRESS

DEREGULATED ELECTRICITY MARKET
ISSUES IN SOUTH-EASTERN EUROPE

Dates: June 22-23, 2026

Venue: Belgrade, Serbia, Mihajlo Pupin
Institute

Under the Aegis of the Region of Crete

ΠΕΡΙΦΕΡΕΙΑ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ
REGION OF CRETE

DEMSEE continues to be the leading regional platform for experts, professionals, and scholars from South-Eastern Europe and beyond, offering the opportunity to present their work, share experiences, and initiate collaborations in the evolving field of electric power systems.

Key Topics:

- Coordination of TSO, DSO, and RCC Operations
- Strategies and Technologies for Blackout Prevention
- RES Integration and Smart Grid Evolution
- Digital Transformation in Power Systems: Digital Twins, AI, and Edge Computing
- Network Codes, Directives, and Policy Frameworks
- Electricity Markets and Power Exchanges
- Electrical Engineering Education for Emerging System Needs
- Advanced Digitalization and Flexibility Solutions to Meet the Growing Demand for Clean Electricity
- Case Studies and Regional Energy Projects in South-East Europe (SEE)

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